

Students' Anxiety in Online Learning and Its Impact to Academic Performance

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11188213>

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Abstract:

Anxiety as an emotion characterized by feelings of tension, worried thoughts, and physical changes like increased blood pressure. Anxiety is a normal and often healthy emotion. However, when a person regularly feels disproportionate levels of anxiety, it might become a medical disorder (Browne, 2020). Individuals with high levels of anxiety generally hold heightened levels of trait anxiety, but in evaluative situations, the state of anxiety also elevates. This descriptive study aimed to identify students' anxiety about online learning and its impact on academic performance. The participants of this study were the 271 students from the first to third years of enrolled in the BEED program at a local city college. Total enumeration was used in conducting the study utilizing quantitative research through the use of validated, modified questionnaires. The results served as the basis for an enhanced program that may be used by the school in the next school year. The student's anxiety and their academic performance in online learning were identified with the modified questionnaire. The Scale of Online Course Anxiety by William Lan et al. The five scales for the level of anxiety were classified into emotional, learning, financial, social, and technological impact. While the three scales in the factors affecting the academic performance of the students were classified into personal, academic, and social factors, The weighted mean is used to calculate the average value of the data. It was found in the study that the student's level of anxiety about online learning affects their academic performance. This paper discussed the factors that affect the level of anxiety of BEED students in online learning and how it impacts their academic performance.

Keywords: Students Anxiety, Online Learning, Academic Performance

Introduction:

Rapid technical advancements, particularly in the areas of video and audio streaming, have enhanced the accessibility of such courses and brought education online. Mandaue City College is one of the institutions in Mandaue City that has adopted online classes with blended learning modalities through the collaboration of Microsoft Teams. Due to the pandemic's widespread effects, online learning is now considered the "New Normal" in Philippine classroom training. Campuses and facilities are closed, face-to-face instruction is prohibited, and classes are held online.

Using the internet for academic purposes is the pivot point of educational attainment in online learning (Sahin, Balta, & Ercan, 2010; Kim, 2011). Nowadays, internet connectivity is nearly universal; for instance, many students have cell phones with online access (Ellore et al., 2014). By gaining access to global information and maintaining excellent contact within the academic community, students can broaden their knowledge, research, and assignments (Siraj et al., 2015).

This research study found out that some students come from rural areas, while others were strapped for cash and had slow internet connections, all of which have an impact on how well they perform in class and affect their grades, making them anxious. Furthermore, as a result of the sudden shift from traditional in-person classroom learning to remote online learning, students encounter specific difficulties. The primary challenges include not being able to get a reliable internet connection, network latency, and financial difficulties that worry students about their academic performance. When studying at home, students face a variety of distractions; not everyone may locate conducive environments and might be limited due to inadequate malware and undependable networks (Zhang et al., 2020). Thus, it led the researchers to identify students' anxiety about online learning and its impact on academic performance among BEED students.

Literature Review:

Online learning was a phrase used to define a learning environment where synchronous and asynchronous academic program management and instructional delivery were done through the internet and other technical methods (Usher & Barak, 2020; Huang, 2019). Asynchronous online learning comprises real-time interactions between the teacher and the students, while synchronous online learning does not have a predetermined schedule for different students. A combination of socioeconomic, psychological, and intellectual reasons led to an increase in the dropout rate among students (Singh & Thurman, 2019).

Pandemics negatively affected students' emotional and behavioral functioning, particularly attention and externalizing problems (i.e., mood and wellness behavior), which are accompanied by uncertainty, isolation, and negative effects on the economy and health (Copeland et al., 2021).

Studies have been conducted to compare online education to traditional classroom instruction in terms of student attitudes, dropout rates, and academic accomplishment. Online learning has a higher dropout rate and was less effective than traditional classroom instruction for a variety of reasons, including the difficulty of the material, the cost, the absence of feedback and encouragement, social isolation, the lack of support, the rules or requirements, and changes in career goals (Pennino et al., 2002).

Most students use their smartphones for online learning because nearly everyone has access to the internet. Students may increase their academic knowledge, do research, and complete projects by having access to material from around the world. This also facilitates simple contact with the academic community (Siraj, 2015). Therefore, researching how internet usage affects student learning outcomes is necessary before using the internet for learning (Ellore, 2014).

Accessed to information can impact students' performance in school (Akende, 2015). Facilitating access to resources and services as well as long-distance communication and collaboration, the use of the Internet for learning is seen as a tool to improve the accessibility, effectiveness, and quality of learning (Kamba, 2009). A lot of individuals have linked Internet use to students' lack of interest in reading, which results in widespread test failure (Alakpodia, 2010).

Research Method:

The study utilized descriptive quantitative research, a type of research method that determined students' anxiety about online learning and their academic performance as perceived by the third-year BEED students of Mandaue City College. Descriptive research was the analysis of data to draw attention to the key traits of data collected or utilized in the study (Fowler, 2013; Siedlecki, 2017). A descriptive research approach could use a variety of research methods to explore one or more variables (Mc Combes, 2019).

The study focused on the Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students, as they often experienced anxiety due to heavy workloads. The participants were 271 students from the first through fourth years of BEED. The study excluded three programs, including Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) majors in English, Filipino, and Math, and four-year BEED students due to their deployment to different schools.

A modified questionnaire was used for data collection, and the Likert scale was applied to analyze the collected data. The modified questionnaire was checked and verified by the three (3) experts for the validity and reliability of the said survey questions using the Survey Instrument Validation Rating Scale. The findings helped the researcher interpret the results.

Findings and Discussion

It is the emotional impact and anxiety level of students participating in online learning. This is presented on the table below. It illustrates the results of the questions related to the emotional impact and anxiety level of students participating in online learning. With five related questions and the descriptive equivalents very High (VH), high (H), low (L), and very Low (VL).

Table 1:
Emotional Impact

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
During online classes, I experience emotional isolation or disconnection.	1.94	H	High
Being absent and not able to attend online class makes me anxious.	2.31	H	High
When I believe I will almost entirely finish the course by myself, I get anxious.	2.11	H	High
Because of the technical difficulties I will inevitably encounter throughout an online course, I am nervous even before it begins.	2.14	H	High
Very slow internet connection makes me angry.	2.52	L	Low
Weighted Mean	2.20	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H); 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L); 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

The table shown that the statement, "I feel emotionally disconnected or isolated during online classes" has the highest emotional impact on students' levels of anxiety in online learning, which corresponds to 1.94. More students were using technology to study rather than link up and fall into a conversation with a person. It increases social isolation and hinders the development of communication skills. Due to their social isolation, they experienced a variety of physical and mental health problems, including stress, insomnia, anxiety, and depressive thoughts that had a severe impact on their academic performance (Cheise, 2023). While the statement "very slow internet connection makes me angry" has the lowest emotional impact when it comes to students' level of anxiety in online learning, which corresponds to 2.52, which means a low level of emotional impact of anxiety in online education.

A dependable internet connection was one of the three difficulties that students faced when learning online (Fabito et al., 2020). It is difficult for students to use the e-learning platform since some do not have access to the internet (Casillano, 2019). According to a number of studies, less privileged children have slow internet connections and don't have access to laptops or desktop computers (Cleofas & Rocha, 2021).

Table 2:
Learning Impact

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
Realizing my learning in an online learning course is so much dependent on technology makes me uncomfortable. I find it unsettling to realize how heavily technology influences my ability to learn in an online course.	2.11	H	High
Due to my lack of familiarity with the online course's platform. I frequently worry that I will forget to turn in assignments.	1.88	H	High
Online classes are unable to provide the necessary communication for in-depth discussion.	2.03	H	High
Limited use of gadgets is preventing me from attending online classes.	1.87	H	High
finding places with good connection affects my online classes	2.23	H	High
Weighted Mean	2.02	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H): 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L): 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

While the statement "finding places with good connections affects my online classes" has the lowest learning impact on a student's level of anxiety, which corresponds to 2.23 (Asio et al., 2021). Access to technology and an internet connection is one of the primary challenges faced to overcome the learning difficulty (Aboagye et al., 2021; Chase et al., 2018; Chung et al., 2020; Lorenzo, 2017), they acknowledged the demands and difficulties associated with internet connections among students. Improved internet connectivity is essential for e-learning, especially in rural areas (Ahmed et al., 2017).

In a different study released in 2017, Hossain and Rahman ordered that student use the internet more effectively for educational purposes. They also advised that the institution provide students with access to online resources and a welcoming environment. Enrolled in classes, 82% of students use the internet for academic purposes (Tarimo & Kavish, 2017). However, a study revealed unfavorable findings about attitudes toward the use of online learning management systems (Serhan, 2020).

Table 3:
Financial Impact

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
I cannot afford weekly or monthly subscription due to lack of financial support.	2.14	H	High
I am anxious that I don't have enough resources to assist my needs in online class	2.23	H	High
I worry of running out of money to pay for load or Wi-Fi subscription.	2.31	H	High
I am worried that my allowance won't be enough to attend online class in a computer shop.	2.00	H	High
I cannot use gadgets to its fullest due to financial expenses constraints.	1.84	H	High
Weighted Mean	2.10	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H): 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L): 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

The results show that the statement “I cannot use gadgets to its fullest due to financial expenses constraints” has the highest financial impact when it comes to students’ level of anxiety in online learning which corresponds to 1.84. Stressed are stress connected to academic, economical, and social concerns has also been linked to distant learning. Additionally, according to the research, the learners’ financial stability is a problem. This suggests that one of the causes of students’ worry is the absence of family income as a result of the students’ lack of online access since students whose parents are economically capable are ultimately controlled by access to online learning (Al Ateeq et al., 2020).

While the statement “I worry about running out of money to pay for a load or Wi-Fi subscription” has the lowest financial impact on students’ level of anxiety in online learning, which corresponds to 2.31. Demonstrated the different educational systems that exist in many countries, both inside and between them (Adarkwah & Day et al., 2021).

In a country that is developing, families from lower socioeconomic strata, like the families of research participants, had limited access to dependable Internet connectivity and online learning tools. People with a high socioeconomic level can obtain sufficient resources, which reduces their susceptibility to psychological discomfort (Rehman et al., 2020).

Table 4:
 Social Impact

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
Increase feeling of isolation and depression because I am unable to socialize and connect with my classmates and instructors due to my signal.	2.01	H	High
I feel behind in terms of group activities in online modality.	1.80	H	High
I’m worried that if I get the incorrect answer, my classmates will make fun of me.	2.23	H	High
I am concerned that the instructor might not recognize each student's unique needs in the absence of face-to-face interaction	2.18	H	High
I am concerned that students taking online courses won't receive the necessary peer support.	2.16	H	High
Weighted Mean	2.08	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H): 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L): 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

While the statement “I’m worried that if I get the incorrect answer, my classmates will make fun of me” has the lowest social impact on students’ level of anxiety in online learning, which corresponds to 2.23.

According to a study, low levels of student confidence might result in low levels of motivation, which can make school mandatory and cause kids to have unfavourable views toward learning by (Palavan, 2017). The results of this study show that self-confidence, not fear, is a crucial predictor of students’ performance, who examined the relationship between speaking anxiety, self-confidence, and the students’ speaking competency (Tridinanti, 2018). The study found that students who had greater self-confidence achieved more, and it advised pupils to do so in order to do better.

Table 5:
 Technological Impact

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
Being disconnected during class due to connectivity problem makes me anxious.	2.50	H	High
Not being able to attend online class due to low battery makes me uncomfortable.	2.41	H	High
I worry that my device will slow me down since it is an old generation device.	2.30	H	High
Unavailability of gadgets hinders my online learning and it makes me worry.	2.24	H	High
I worry that my internet connection will fail every time I enter the virtual classroom.	2.42	H	High
Weighted Mean	2.08	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H): 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L): 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

The results show that the statement “unavailability of gadgets hinders my online learning and it makes me worry” has the highest technological impact on students’ level of anxiety in online learning, which corresponds to 2.24. Online learning is a sort of learning where learning experiences take place in synchronous or asynchronous environments (Dhawan, 2020). Online learning as the process of delivering education via the use of digital tools like the Internet and mobile devices like laptops and smartphones (Al-Busaidi, 2013).

On the other hand, it is said that online learning is totally focused on learning through the use of technology, most likely computers and other modern tools (Ahmad 2012). From wherever they are, students can communicate with teachers and fellow college students (Singh & Thurman, 2019).

Additionally, study discovered that students who had access to internet-connected devices had considerably more favorable attitudes toward embracing online learning options (Alzahrani & O’Toole’s, 2017).

This implies that, if necessary, students might use any online learning environment. Students will agree to participate in online learning programs if they have access to the essential internet-connected equipment and can utilize it (Afolayan, 2015; Leszczyski et al., 2018). While the statement “Being disconnected during class due to connectivity problems makes me anxious” has the lowest technological impact on students’ level of anxiety, which corresponds to 2.50.

The Philippines’ poor Internet connection is a result of out-of-date Philippine law and bureaucracy, which hinder the quick installation of mobile towers (Natividad, 2021; Salac & Kim, 2016). 20% of college students struggled to keep up with their access to technology, particularly internet connectivity (Gonzales et al., 2018). The sudden transition to emergency online distribution and the widespread shut down of campus facilities had made the problem fairly obvious. Studies that all draw attention to the technological problems that can affect how well students and instructors participate in online learning, particularly with synchronous content. High-speed internet accessibility is one of these problems. (Skinner’s, 2019; Rasheed, et al., 2020; Raes, et al., 2019; Zydny, et al., 2019).

Anxiety is used to describe the emotions of concern, dread, and unease. It is a feeling of concern from information technology being misused and affecting course success. (Saadé, Kira, Mak, & Nebebe, 2017). It is shown in the table below the summary of the level of anxiety of the students in Mandaue City College from first year to third year.

Table 6
Summary of the Level of Anxiety

STATEMENTS	Mean	DE	Interpretation
Emotional Impact	2.20	H	High
Learning Impact	2.02	H	High
Financial Impact	2.10	H	High
Social Impact	2.08	H	High
Technological Impact	2.08	H	High
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.10	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H); 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L); 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

The result shows the general weighted mean of all the impacts on students’ levels of anxiety that affect their academic performance. It was found that the Emotional Impact was the highest, which corresponds to 2.20. Within the first two weeks of studying at home, students have begun to grow weary of online learning, and mood fluctuations are brought on by having too many assignments, which are regarded as unproductive by students (Irawan, 2020).

Table 7
Summary of Factors Affecting Students Anxiety

STATEMENTS	WM	DE	Interpretation
Personal Factors	2.28	H	High
Academic Factor	1.77	H	High
Social Factor	1.87	H	High
WEIGHTED MEAN	2.09	H	High

Legend: Very High (VH): 1.0 to 1.75; High (H); 1.76 to 2.50; Low (L); 2.51 to 3.25; and Very Low (VL): 3.26 to 4.0.

The table displayed the overall weighted mean of all the variables determining students' levels of anxiety and how well they performed academically. It was found that the personal factor was the highest factor in a student's anxiety that affects their academic performance, which corresponds to 2.28. Online training is less motivating and more anxiety-inducing than in-person instruction. Connection problems, the absence of visibility in non-verbal replies, and the instructor's teaching approach were all noted as important aspects (Zuniga, 2022).

Conclusion:

This study concludes that BEED students at Mandaue City College experience high levels of anxiety in online learning, which negatively impacts their academic performance. The study suggests that students' ability to observe and imitate behaviors of their peers on social media during online classes contributes to distractions and heightened anxiety, as per Albert Bandura's Social Cognitive Theory. Additionally, slow internet connectivity has a significant emotional impact on BEED students, further affecting their academic performance, in line with the E-Learning Theory by Haxia He. To address these issues, the researchers introduced a program called "Students' Awareness on Mental Support and Well Being." However, it's important to note that the findings may not apply universally to all universities, as they can vary based on individual circumstances and environments.

Limitations and Further Research:

There are three (3) programs under education that are not included in the study. These are the Bachelor of Secondary Education (BSED) majors in English, Filipino, and Math because this study only focused on Bachelor of Elementary Education (BEED) students as the research respondents. The BEED respondents who were absent during our survey were not included in the study, and those with difficulty participating in this study due to personal problems, refusal to give informed consent, or refusal to participate in this research study were also not included in the research study.

This study also did not include the four-year BEED students because they were not available on the school premises during the time that the researcher conducted the study because they were deployed to different schools for their practice teaching.

References:

- Abdous, M. 2019. The Internet and Higher Education 41, 34-44, 2019. Influence of satisfaction and preparedness on online students' feelings of anxiety. Center for Learning and Teaching, 336 Gornito Hall, Old Dominion University, Norfolk, VA 23529, USA.
- Affum, M. (2022). THE EFFECT OF INTERNET ON STUDENTS' STUDIES: A REVIEW, *Library Philosophy and Practice* (e-journal). 6932, pp. 1-20.
- Agung, A. Surtikanti, M. Quinones, C. 2020. Students' perception of online learning during COVID-19 pandemic: A case study on the English students of STKIP Pamane Talino. Saint Paul University Manila, Pedro Gil St., Malate, Manila, Philippines.
- Arribathi, A., Suwanto, Rosyad, A., Budiarto, M., Supriyanti, D. & Mulyati (2021). An Analysis of Student Learning Anxiety During the COVID-19 Pandemic: A Study in Higher Education, *The Journal of Continuing Higher Education*, 69:3, 192-205, DOI: 10.1080/07377363.2020.1847971.
- Chung, E., Noor, N.M., & Mathew V.N. (2020). Are you ready? An assessment of online learning Readiness among university students. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education & Development*, 9(1), 301-317.

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This is to certify that Lobitaña et' al. submitted their manuscript in this office titled **"Students' Anxiety in Online Learning and its Impact to Academic Performance"** has undergone plagiarism checking via **Plagiarism Detector Apps**. The results were as follows:

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This certification is issued to Lobitaña et' al. on the 24th day of June 2023 for whatever legal purpose this may serve best.

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The research entitled "Students' Anxiety in Online Learning and its Impact to Academic Performance" of Angeline Lobitaña, Dexter James G. Tubio, Liza Marie Makiling, Riza P. Bañados, & Jane Angel Comcom, has been thoroughly read and corrected by me as the Research Censor and the manuscript has been edited by the student-researchers.

After compliance with the comments and suggestions given, they have made revisions which are now considered to meet the standard for a quality research output.

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CERTIFICATION FOR GRAMMAR CHECK

Name of Grammarian: Melojie Lauron

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This is to certify that the study entitled "Students' Anxiety in Online Learning and its Impact to Academic Performance" of Angeline Lobitaña, Dexter James G. Tubio, Liza Marie Makiling, Riza P. Bañados, & Jane Angel Comcom, Bachelor of Elementary Education students of Mandaue City College has been checked by Melojie Lauron as Grammarian.

This certification is issued upon request of the group as part of their oral defense requirements.

Given this 25th day of June 2023.

MELOJIE R. LAURON

Signature over the printed name
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